

Introduction

In the year 1952, India started a nationwide Family Planning Programme in order to control the population growth. This programme was a pioneering approach by the government of India. The programme stressed on various contraceptive methods while highlighting sterilization, a permanent contraceptive method. During the 1970's, the then Indira Gandhi Government tried implementing a forced sterilization programme where men with two or more children were asked to submit themselves to sterilization. The force involved in implementing the programme created a general apathy in the minds of the Indian masses towards family planning (Wikipedia, 2011). Over the years the programme changed its direction and perspective in order to embrace wider goals of maternal and child health, nutrition and family welfare in keeping with the global goal of reproductive health rights.

The International Conference on Population and Development, Cairo, 1994, can be observed as a milestone in the history of population and development. India, one among the 179 signatory countries vowed to provide universal access to family planning and sexual and reproductive health services and reproductive rights in order to specially empower women. It recognized that women have the right to establish a family, the right to decide on the number, timing and spacing of children, the right to have access to the information and means needed to exercise voluntary choices, the right to the highest attainable standard of health. They are also rights that women and young women in particular are unable to access (UNECLAC, 2004).

Contraception or birth control or fertility control as it is variously called is the use of devices or methods to prevent pregnancy. There are two methods of contraception – temporary and permanent or reversible

Article

Contraceptive Knowledge and Use among Married Women in an Urban Slum

Gargi Lahiri

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8290634

Abstract

India is the pioneering country to have initiated a Family Planning Programme as early as 1951 in order to stabilize population explosion. From its initiation till now, the concept and approach of the programme have changed many times keeping with the global goal of Reproductive Health rights. The contraceptive scenario in India reveals that the use of contraception is on the rise. The use of a particular method of contraception is principally governed by the knowledge of the method. In this paper, an attempt has been made to see the knowledge and use of any contraceptive method- both reversible and irreversible, among urban slum dwelling married women of reproductive age.

Keywords: Family planning, Reproductive health rights, Contraception, Reversible and Irreversible methods of contraception.

²Research Scholar (Ph.D.), Department of Sociology, The University of Burdwan & Faculty-Department of Hospital Management, George College (Affiliated to West Bengal University of Technology), Kolkata.

and irreversible. The reversible methods include a wide range of both short term and long term devices in the form of Oral Contraceptive Pills(OCPs), Intra Uterine devices (IUDs), condoms(both male and female), injectables etc while irreversible methods include male and female sterilization, popularly known as vasectomy and tubectomy or ligation. Ligation ends a woman's ability to conceive while hormonal (OCPs, injections) and barrier contraceptives (Condoms, IUDs) interrupts women's ability to conceive only when in use (Siqueira et al, 2007). The Govt. of India Family Planning programme offers 3 methods of reversible contraception-pills, IUDs and the condom.

The last two decades have found that India is also heading towards small families with greater acceptability and utilization of family planning methods. Both knowledge and utilization of contraceptive methods have increased in the country. This is well reflected in the growth rate and total fertility rate in the country. The growth rate has recorded a phenomenal low since independence while the national TFR stands at

2.6. TFR of some of the states show outstanding performance such as Kerala (1.7), West Bengal, Maharashtra and Punjab (1.9). According to NFHS 3, the country shows almost universal knowledge of contraceptives. Among the permanent modern Family Planning methods, female sterilization was the most popular Over 97 percent of women and 95 percent men know about female sterilization. Male sterilization, by contrast, is known only by 79 percent of women and 87 percent of men. Ninety-three percent of men know about condoms, compared with 74 percent of women. More than 80 percent women and men know about contraceptive pills ((FAMILY WELFARE STATISTICS IN INDIA 2011, Statistics Division Ministry of Health and Family Welfare Government of India., 2011)). According to (National Family Health Survey (NFHS-3), 2007) about 37% of the currently married women are female sterilization adopters. During the period, the country's contraceptive prevalence rate was 56%. Out of these, 66% of women were female sterilization users. On the

other hand, the percentage of couples relying on male sterilization was 3 % only (Singh et al, 2012).

Thus, a dominance of female sterilization over other contraceptive methods is seen from the national data. A report in (Bloomberg on June 12, 2013) says that India sterilizes 4.6 million women each year, thereby accounting for 37% of the global sterilization. Female sterilization as a percentage of total contraceptive use in India as against the global average is shown by the following graph.

Source: (Guilford, 2013)

Rationale for the study

Knowledge of and access to contraceptives empowers men and women to make their own reproductive choice and hence improved reproductive health. Contraceptive use help reduce maternal mortality by helping women delay, space and limit pregnancies. It aids in weeding out the risks arising on account of numerous and frequent pregnancies and those from unsafe abortions due to unintended pregnancies (USAID, 2013). A glimpse of some figures will lead to a better understanding of the above facts regarding contraceptives –

222 million women in the developing world want to avoid pregnancy but are not utilizing contraceptives.

2 in 5 pregnancies in the developing world are unintended.

Unintended pregnancies can have dire consequences for mothers and their babies.

Complications during pregnancy and childbirth kill near 785 women every day.

By spacing and limiting pregnancies contraceptives save the lives of mothers and their children.

Using contraceptives to plan pregnancies could prevent 1 in 3 maternal deaths.

Spacing pregnancies by more than 3 years reduces the under 5 mortality by 25%.

Objectives of Study

Keeping the above stated things in mind, a study was undertaken in a slum at a town in Hooghly district of West Bengal with the following objectives

To gain an understanding of the knowledge of various reversible and irreversible contraceptive methods among slum dwelling married women of reproductive age.

To trace the source of such knowledge or information.

To find the use of various contraceptive methods among such women.

Review of Literature

A number of studies all across the globe have found that female sterilization dominates most of the parts of the world despite its irreversibility. A study in Brazilian Amazon basin found that about 40% of all

married women between 15 – 49 years are sterilized. The reliance on sterilization is greater since the pills and IUDs needs to be purchased and lack of information on long lasting reversible methods (Siqueira et al, 2007). Another UK based study on reversible and irreversible methods of contraception found that though sterilization is popular and a satisfactory choice but the failure and regret rates are also not as low as expected. Despite the failure rates, women principally chose sterilization because of the irreversibility, no hormonal side effects and not to take future child bearing decisions any more (Kane et al, 2009). Another study put forth a range of characteristics which a long acting reversible contraceptive should have to achieve greatest potential in developing countries with low levels of literacy. The contraceptive should be safe, have minimal side effects, fully reversible, little or no need for action on the part of the user once accepted, no need for continuing supplies and low cost (Moskowitz & Jennings, 1996). A study on sterilization regret in India found that about 5% of sterilized women regret it shortly after sterilization. The regret rate varies with age of sterilization, years of sterilization, sex composition of children, experience of child loss and region of residence (Singh et al, 2012).

Materials and Methods

Study Location - A slum in a town in Hooghly district of West Bengal was chosen as the study place.

Sampling Method - the study used Snowball Sampling method. It is defined as a technique for gathering research subjects through the identification of an initial subject who is used to provide the names of the actors. These actors may themselves open possibilities for an expanding web of contact and enquiry (Faugier & Sargeant, 1997).

Sample Size - 43 participants were gathered initially using snowball sampling method. A local social worker gathered few married women who showed interest in

participating in the study. They were all in the age range

Work status	No. of participants	Percentage of participants
Working	34	85%
Non Working	06	15%
Total	40	100%

15-45 years and who in turn identified other interested women in the same age range. But, after knowing about the sensitive topic, 3 women declined to participate. So, 40 married women participated in the study finally. Since all women were Bengali speaking the interviews were conducted in Bengali.

Data Collection - A semi structured questionnaire was used for collecting information from the participant women. Women were asked directly about their knowledge of various methods, the source of such knowledge and personal use through in depth interview using a semi structured questionnaire.

Data Analysis - Collected data were tabulated and analyzed in the form of percentages and represented in the tables.

Limitations of the study

One major limitation of the study is that it adopted a non-random sampling method called snowball sampling, where there are chances for bias to creep in since the respondents identify other potential respondents.

Data Tabulation

Table 1: Characteristics of the participants by age group

Gender	Marital status	Age group	No. of participants	Percentage of participants
Female	Married	15-24 years	08	20%
		25-34 years	22	55%
		35-45 years	10	25%
		Total	40	100%

Table 2: Work status of the participants

Table 3: Knowledge of Reversible and Irreversible contraceptive methods among married women in urban slum

Item	Reversible methods	Irreversible methods	Total
Knowledge of Contraceptive methods	10 (25%)	30 (75%)	40(100%)

Table 4: Usage pattern of Reversible and Irreversible contraceptive methods among married women in urban slum

Item	Reversible methods	Irreversible methods	Presently not using any method	Total
Usage of Contraceptive methods	08 (20%)	28 (70%)	04 (10%)	40(100%)

Table 5: Main Source of knowledge of various methods of Contraception

Source	Number of Women	Percentage of Women
Doctor / other Health workers	07	17.5%
Family members	13	32.5%
Friends / Peer group	16	40.0%
Radio / Television	04	10.0%
Total	40	100%

Results

Age, Educational and Working status of the participants

Table 1 shows the number of participants in various age groups. It was found that 20% of the participants were in the age group of 15 – 24 years, 55% in the age group of 25-34 years and 25% in the age group of 35-45 years. Among the 40 participants, 22(55%) were found to be literate and 18(45%) were illiterate. The distribution of literacy levels of 22 participants showed that 17 of them had their primary education in local municipal school whereas 5 completed their middle school. None of them was reported to go to high school. Table 2 shows the working status of the participants which reveals that 34(85%) of them are working and 6(15%) of them are homemakers. Among the working females, 33(97%) are found to be engaged in the informal sector as they work as domestic helps in the area. 1(3%) has been found to work as an Auxiliary Nurse & Midwife in a nursing home (formal sector).

Knowledge of Contraceptive methods

All the 40 participants were asked about their knowledge of contraceptive methods, both reversible and non reversible. Table 3 summarizes the knowledge of reversible and irreversible methods of contraception among all the participants. The reversible methods included hormonal contraceptives like OCPs, emergency pills and barrier contraceptives like I.U.D and male condoms to be used by their husbands. The irreversible methods included the knowledge of vasectomy in males and tubectomy or tubal ligation in females. Knowledge here meant whether they have heard of the methods and their ability to cite an example of the same. The knowledge and ever usage pattern were determined separately for the literate and the illiterate participants. It was found that 25% of all participants knew about reversible methods whereas 75% knew about irreversible methods.

The contraceptive knowledge of illiterate females was found to be lower than their literate counterparts for all reversible and irreversible methods. Further probe into knowledge revealed that among the reversible methods knowledge of OCPs were the highest, then male condoms with IUD and emergency pills known to relatively less participants.

Source of Knowledge of Contraceptive Methods

The participant women were asked about their chief source of knowledge of various methods of contraception. Table 5 shows the results of such source. It is seen that 40% women identified their friends or peer group as the chief source for disseminating contraceptive knowledge. In 32.5% of the cases significant family members like mothers were the chief source of knowledge whereas 17.5% and 10% of the participants identified the doctors or other health workers and mass media like TV or radio as the source of knowledge.

Use of Contraceptive Methods

All women in the study population were asked about their (or their husband's) ever use of any reversible method and use of irreversible methods of contraception. It was found that 8 (20%) women currently used a reversible method whereas 28 (70%) of them resorted to an irreversible method. On enquiring the 20% reversible method users it was found that 6 of them use OCPs while only a single woman reported to have an IUD implantation and another woman reported the use of condom by her husband. The extremely limited use of male condoms among the participants drive our attention to the vulnerability of these females to sexually transmitted diseases.

Use of irreversible methods of contraception showed an overwhelming response to female ligation among the participants. 27 participants have resorted to ligation as a permanent solution. Uses of male sterilization have been remarkably low with data showing only 1 husband sterilized. This suggests that it is principally the female's responsibility to adopt family planning as is evident from the above data. The results have been summarized in Table 5. A closer look at the age of the sterilized females revealed that a significant number of them underwent sterilization at a very early age i.e., 25 – 34 years. Researchers have found that there has been a decline in the age of sterilization in India and instances of regretting sterilization at an early age is not uncommon (Singh et al, 2012), International Perspectives on Sexual and Reproductive Health. Table 4 shows that 4 women (10%) did not use any contraceptive methods. Interview revealed that 1 woman was married for 2 months only, another was deserted by husband after 6 months of marriage, third woman had a hysterectomy operation done after the birth of second child and the fourth was in her post-menopausal phase and had 3 living children.

Discussion

It has been found that 75% of the females among the participants have the knowledge of tubal ligation

(female sterilization). But, apart from OCPs, none of the other methods of reversible sterilization are familiar among women. 22 women out of 40 (55%) had been either to a primary or middle school but strangely enough none of them had clear knowledge about female and male anatomy, menstrual cycle, safe sex period. All of them reported that there had been no classes in schools or by health workers in order to impart such knowledge. The source of knowledge can largely be attributed to the peer group, followed by family members like mothers in most cases. Media like radio and television also played some role in disseminating contraceptive knowledge. The women who reported gathering the knowledge from doctors or other health workers were further asked during in depth interview regarding which things they were told about contraception. All women replied that they were told about OCPs, condoms and ligation only. But, they were not advised thoroughly regarding them. Those with 2 or more children were referred to go to the local general hospital to get their ligation done. The pros and cons of none of the methods were explained and choices were limited to OCPs and ligation. Women blindly accepted these methods due to ignorance of the other reversible long lasting methods. So, the element of informed choice was absent. The stress on adopting irreversible method of contraception by the health workers may be due to the incentives they receive per case (Rs. 150 per case).

Studying all participants by their use of reversible contraceptive methods reveal that OCPs had been the major tool for family planning. Women were asked about their dependence on OCPs during the interview. The reasons for using OCPs were their affordability (a packet of Mala-D costs Rs.10 only), easy accessibility in local pharmacy and negligible side effects. When asked whether they get it for free from health workers, one of the respondent replied "I got it only once during my 5 year marriage. We don't depend on them. We get it for Rs. 10 from the nearby medicine shop." The health workers working in the area also affirmed that the supply of OCPs and condoms are

limited, so, it is not possible to meet the needs of all clients.

Notable in the study is the finding that only 1 woman reported that her husband used condoms during intercourse. When probed for the reason behind non use of condoms, one of the replies was "My husband says that condom interferes with the sexual pleasure during intercourse." Another woman said "Most of the days my husband returns home drunk. Can I ask somebody to use a condom when he is not in his senses?" Another said that "We do not have privacy in our one room house. Often the children come across the condom packet and ask us embarrassing questions. Thus it is better for me to use pills." One woman said "It is the woman's responsibility to give birth to and rear children. So, we need to take protection and not our husbands. They are busy with the outside world. Hence, it is us who should use pills in order to prevent further births. Then, when husband agree we go for ligation".

This reflects that most women believe that the major responsibility to avoid conception falls on them only and not their husbands.

The fact that condoms also help to prevent sexually transmitted diseases were not known by 38(95%) respondents. One woman who knew about it is working as a midwife at a nursing home and the other had the information from the radio advertisements of National Aids Control Organization (NACO). No women including those who have completed their primary and middle schools could give an example of a sexually transmitted disease (STD). When asked whether they have heard about HIV/AIDS, those having exposure to T.V and radio replied "You mean Buladi, right..we have heard about it...but would not be able to tell anything more."

The interviews also revealed several misconceptions about various methods of contraception. It was found in the study that only 2 women have ever used IUD. When others were asked that why don't they opt for a long term contraceptive measure like IUD, few misconceptions came to surface. "Its very painful...the devices have the chance of cutting

through the intestine and lead to death", was one reply. Another said, " its too costly...it will lead to serious discomfort and I would no longer be able to lead a normal sexual life". However, among the 2 IUD ever users, 1 reported of discomfort shortly after implant and had to get it removed. Misconceptions about vasectomy or male sterilization is also common – it leads to physical weakness and deprives a man of his sexual relationships is the commonest. One woman said that even after vasectomy one can have a child. She has seen such a person at her native village. This calls for health workers to inform the general masses about the reality that vasectomy is simpler than tubal ligation and it does not involve any undesirable side effects.

3 women reported history of abortions. Out of which 1 woman said that she had 2 spontaneous abortions while the other 2 had 1 induced abortion each. But, in the latter 2 instances, both the women did not disclose the place where they got it done. 6 women reported getting pregnant while using OCPs but when asked regarding the rules of taking OCPs; it was revealed that they did not take them continuously. Often there were gaps in taking the OCPs. In their words "it is difficult to remember it every day. Sometimes we forget to take them due to our busy household chores. Sometimes we do not have the money to buy it."

This type of contraceptive behavior implies a high risk of unintended pregnancies and poor maternal and child health.

Interview with the sterilized women to know the reliance on female sterilization revealed that the burden of avoiding unintended pregnancy chiefly lies on them and they rely more on a permanent solution to the problem. Hence the choice of ligation. Also, the uses of other short and long lasting reversible methods imply their buying on a regular or periodic basis. Women who work day in and day out to make both ends meet find the purchase of such contraceptive devices out of their reach. So, the use gets stunted due to lack of affordability. On the contrary, women opting for sterilization is given a cash reward on the part of the

Government. All these somehow compel women to resort to sterilization.

Conclusion

It has been found that there is a lack of information among these slum dwelling women regarding various methods of contraception. This situation calls for attention to be given to "sex education" in schools as well as by community health workers. This will go a long way in weeding out the misconceptions and ignorance about male and female anatomy, various reversible and irreversible methods of family planning and help couples in making wiser decisions regarding spacing and limiting births.

It has also been found that the supplies of condoms and OCPs in health centres are not sufficient to fulfill their demands. There are a sizable portion of people who depend on these supplies as they cannot afford to buy them from the market. Irregular and limited supply of these essential contraceptive devices will expose these people to the risk of unintended pregnancies and sexual ill health. Thus, the Government should arrange for an free, uninterrupted and sufficient supply of family planning tools in order to help people attain a better reproductive and sexual health.

Absence of information on long lasting reversible methods, inability to buy reversible contraceptives, irregular use of reversible contraceptives forces a sizable portion of the women of reproductive age to resort to sterilization at a very early age of their reproductive life. Regret is also often associated with such sterilization. The NFHS 2005-2006 reveals that 4.6% of sterilized women in the country exhibit sterilization regret (Singh et al, International Perspectives on Sexual and Reproductive Health, 2012).

The situation thus demands strong action on the part of the Govt. to find long lasting reversible methods of contraception which should be as good as the irreversible method to avoid unintended pregnancies.

Bibliography

- Bloomberg on June 12. (2013). Sterilization. India: Bloomberg. Quartz. Retrieved 5 July 2014, from <http://www.qz.com/93679>
- Family Welfare Statistics in India (2011). Statistics Division. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare Government of India. Retrieved July 05, 2014 from http://www.2cnpop.net/uploads/1/0/2/1/10215849/mohfw_statistics_2011_revised_31_10_11.pdf
- Faugier, J. & Sargeant, M . (1997). Sampling Hard-to-Reach Populations. *Medipub* , 26(4), 790-797.
- Guilford, G. (2014). The world's biggest sterilizer of women isn't China—it's India. Quartz. Retrieved 5 July 2014, from <http://www.qz.com/93679/the-worlds-biggest-female-sterilizer-isnt-china-its-india/>
- Hall, M., Stephenson, R., & Juvekar, S. (2008). Social and logistical barriers to the use of reversible contraception among women in a rural Indian village. *Journal of Health, Population, And Nutrition*, 26(2), 241-250. Retrieved 7 July 2014, from <http://www.bioline.org.br/pdf?hn08026>
- ICPD - International Conference on Population and Development Beyond 2014, (2014). ICPD - Reproductive Health & Rights. Retrieved 7 July 2014, from <http://icpdbeyond2014.org/rights-development/view/7-reproductive-health-rights>
- Kane et al. (2009). Long-acting, reversible and permanent methods of contraception: insight into women's choice of method. Retrieved 5 July 2014, from <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/24402815>

Moskowitz, E., & Jennings, B. (1996). *Coerced Contraception?* Georgetown University Press. [Press.georgetown.edu](http://press.georgetown.edu). Retrieved 7 July 2014, from <http://press.georgetown.edu/book/georgetown/coerced-contraception>

National Family Health Survey (NFHS-3). (2007). International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) and Macro International. 2007. National Family Health Survey (NFHS-3), 2005–06: India: Volume I. Mumbai: IIPS.

Singh, A., Ogollah, R., Ram, F., & Pallikadavath, S. (2012). Sterilization Regret Among Married Women in India: Implications for the Indian National Family Planning Program. *IPSRH*, 38(04), 187-195. doi:10.1363/3818712

Siqueira, Andréa D.; Álvaro D'Antona,; Maria D'Antona,; Emilio Moran,. "Embodied Decisions: Reversible and Irreversible Contraceptive Methods among Rural Women in the Brazilian Amazon." *Human Organization. Society for Applied Anthropology*. 2007. Retrieved July 07, 2014 from HighBeam Research:<http://www.highbeam.com/doc/1P3-1309004761.html>

Usaid.gov,. (2014). U.S. Agency for International Development. Retrieved 7 July 2014, from <http://www.usaid.gov/>

UNECLAC. (2004). United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2004. USAID. (2013).

Wikipedia. (2011). Family Planning in India. Retrieved 04 02, 2014, from Wikipedia: